

Alberta Precambrian Basement: Implications for EGS development

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Abstract

The Precambrian basement underlying the Western Canadian Sedimentary Basin has recently become the subject of geothermal study. In order to implement an enhanced geothermal system in the Alberta Precambrian Basement, one must first understand the reactivity potential and the potential of the in-situ rocks to transmit fluid. In this paper, we present data pertaining to the specific surface areas of the basement rocks and the implications for EGS development. This opens the pathway for future research into the development of an EGS system in the basement rocks.

1. Introduction

The Alberta Precambrian basement underlies the Western Canadian Sedimentary Basin, ranging from a maximum depth of approximately six kilometers in the West, to outcropping at the surface in the Northeastern portion of the province. The basement rocks range in age from 1.7 billion, to 3.5 billion years old as determined through monazite and zircon ages (Ross 2002, Pană 2003). The lithologies that underlie the basement are dominantly crystalline, with protoliths being of both igneous and clastic sedimentary origin. Grades of metamorphism range from lower greenschist to upper amphibolite facies (Pană 2003) and almost all rocks display some characteristics of alteration by hot fluids.

The Alberta Precambrian basement has a limited dataset of cored wells which have intersected the basement due to extensive oil and gas exploration in the basin since the mid twentieth century. Thus, tectonic subdivisions of the basement have been determined on the basis of gravimetric and aeromagnetic survey data. From this, Ross (1990) divided the basement into 22 terranes and inferred several magmatic and shear zones. There are many terranes for which there is no core available, and future exploration into those terranes' geothermal potential may be warranted.

Previous works by Banks and Harris (2014) wherein basement rock properties were determined through analysis of their natural permeabilities and porosities have laid the groundwork for the determination of EGS potential. In their works, they also determined the lithologies of basement cores taken from within the

Talston Magmatic Zone on the south shores of Lake Athabasca. It was determined that natural hydrological characteristics were not sufficient for fluid flow, and as such, an enhanced geothermal system would be necessary for geothermal development in many areas of Alberta. This is also due to the fact that the basin does not typically possess a geothermal gradient high enough to produce temperatures above 120°C within sedimentary rocks.

Due to the immense cost which an EGS would require, one must be assured of the level of reactivity of the basement rocks in order to avoid precipitation of unwanted minerals. This level of reactivity may be predicted qualitatively through the usage of specific surface area measurements. These measurements are of how much surface area of the rock is available to react with surrounding fluids and either dissolve or react with the fluid. Additionally, identifying the mineralogy of the rocks is of use as one may be able to predict reactions and dissolution occurring within the reservoir.

2. Methods and techniques

Six wells were identified as being of interest and were analyzed using various methods. Specific surface areas of basement rocks were determined by using the Autosorb IQ BET machine, which measures the specific surface area of the samples based on the adsorption and desorption characteristics of the sample. Rock samples were powdered to a consistent grain size, and two grams of powder were then analyzed. Additionally, thin section analysis and electron microprobe data were obtained in order to determine the composition of these basement rocks.

3. Results

The results of the specific surface area measurements for the six wells can be found in **Table 1**.

Thin section analysis of these basement rocks details pervasive alteration due to fluid-rock interaction in many samples. Pyrite, hematite, and sericite are the dominant alteration products identified through thin section analysis. All wells show some degree of alteration, with at least one of the aforementioned phases present.

Table 1 - Specific Surface Areas of Alberta Precambrian Basement Rocks

Well Number	Lithology	Specific Surface Area (m ² /g)
1	K-mica Chlorite Biotite Gneiss	2.0981
2	Chloritized Paragneiss	3.8670
3	Biotite Chlorite Gneiss	0.5854
4	Biotite Gneiss	2.9622
5	Altered Metasediment	4.9199
7	Orthogneiss	0.5215

Electron microprobe data was obtained for four wells which were of interest. It was found that within several wells which possessed infilled fractures, the minerals infilling fractures were quartz, calcite, phengite, clinozoisite, pyrite, and clays.

4. Discussion

Previous works which have laid the groundwork for the development of an EGS have already showed that stimulation of the reservoir is a necessity for fluid flow. However, whether or not chemical stimulation would be effective was not clear. With a more accurate representation of vein mineralogy given by electron microprobe and thin section analysis here, an effective chemical stimulation plan may be able to be performed. However, without full core and fracture data analyses, it may be difficult to quantify the effect which that stimulation would have on the reservoir.

Specific surface areas of the basement rocks are within a wide range and reflect the heterogeneity and complexities of the geological history of the Alberta Precambrian Basement. It can be stated that those wells with a high specific surface area have more evidence of alteration than those without large amounts of alteration products. Additionally, mafic lithologies have a higher specific surface area than felsics, which is to be expected as mafic rocks are typically more reactive than felsic rocks. This increased specific surface area in specific wells would likely lead to more dissolution in the reservoir and thus increased precipitation in the system, decreasing effectiveness. It can be inferred that unaltered felsic rocks will make more effective reservoir than altered mafic rocks.

5. Conclusions

Basement rocks properties have been compiled on six wells which intersect the Alberta Precambrian Basement, resulting in a sound foundation for future study into the possibility of an EGS. There exists a natural fracture

system within the basement in many wells, but the fractures have been infilled with mostly quartz, calcite, phengite, clinozoisite, pyrite, and clay minerals being the dominant phases. Additionally, specific surface areas of these rocks were determined, and the trend was for those rocks with more pervasive alteration to have a higher specific surface area. The potential for an effective geothermal system within the Alberta Precambrian Basement is much higher than the basin in many cases, and as such, warrants further investigation.

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References

- Pană, D., Precambrian Basement of the Western Canada sedimentary basin in Northern Alberta, Alberta Energy and Utilities Board, Alberta Geologic Survey, 2003
- Ross, G. M., Parrish, R. R., Villeneuve, M. E. and Bowring, S. A., Geophysics and geochronology of the crystalline basement of the Alberta Basin, western Canada Canadian Journal of Earth Sciences, Canadian Science Publishing, **1991**, Vol. 28(4), pp. 512-522
- Banks, J., Harris N., Developing Alberta's Geothermal Reserves with the EGS-CO2 Method, 2014
- Ross, G. M. (2002). Evolution of Precambrian continental lithosphere in western Canada: Results from lithoprobe studies in Alberta and beyond. Canadian Journal of Earth Sciences, 39(3), 413-437.